

THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND THEIR IMPORTANCE IN INCREASING THE LEVEL OF CHILDREN'S LEARNING

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Annotation: *In this article, the method of using multimedia technologies in the process of educating preschool children, its impact on children, the procedure for using multimedia technologies, the importance of multimedia technology in the effectiveness of preschool education, supporting the interest of children using multimedia technologies in the cooperation of preschool education organizations and families, methods of orientation to learning are highlighted.*

Key words: *Organization of preschool education, multimedia, technology, media education, preschool age.*

Nowadays, there are almost no areas where modern technologies have not penetrated. In particular, modern technologies are used in the process of educating children of preschool age. These technologies have been showing their effectiveness in the comprehensive development of children. In our country, the stage of revealing the potential possibilities of the educational process, based on the implementation of modern pedagogical technologies in educational practice, continues. At the same time, educators are trying to improve educational efficiency and quality by introducing innovative technologies into the educational process. With the development of modern technologies, multimedia has become an important technique used in teaching children.

The dictionary meaning of the term multimedia (multim-medium or multi-media) is composed of two sets of words and means multi, media-environment. In scientific and educational literature, the term is interpreted as "multimedia", "multimedia environment", "multilayered environment", "information carrier". The concept of "multimedia" is explained in different ways in the literature. Among them, it is defined as "Multimedia means a set of tools that process information in various forms."

Multimedia is a special technology, based on software and technical equipment, it is an opportunity to simultaneously express textual, visual

information with sound and movement on a computer. Multimedia is a tool capable of working with visual information. Usually, it means multimedia. means a complex of data processing tools of various forms. Multimedia is a modern information technology that allows incorporating text, sound, video and various animations into a computer system.

Education based on multimedia technology provides an interesting learning environment that helps children learn easily.

The specific features and advantages of multimedia can be described as follows:

- There is a possibility of deeper and more perfect mastering of the given materials;
- Multimedia reinforces children's knowledge gained during the educational process through practice;
- Saves time in the teaching process;
- Enables practical learning;
- It allows to strengthen the knowledge acquired in the preschool education organization in cooperation with the family and ensures that it is kept in memory for a long time;
- Facilitates individual and team learning;
- It ensures children's interest in the educational process.

In the process of education, it develops children's ability to create independently.

Media education has its place in the educational process as an interactive method that affects the child individually. Media education teaches a child to increase his logical thinking, to think independently, to develop creative activities, to draw conclusions. One of the most important tasks of media education is to teach the young generation to use all kinds of information correctly and purposefully in the age of increasingly fast technologies. Media education encourages the integration of learned information, the expression of personal opinion based on this, and retrieval. In order to use multimedia in education, the educator must first of all have sufficient knowledge on the use of multimedia tools. That is why today it is a state requirement to be able to use modern technologies in every field.

Classes conducted using multimedia technology are based on computer technology. It should be noted that students cannot sit in front of the computer for more than 15 minutes during the training. It should be noted that in the "State Requirements for the Education of Preschool Children" the child should spend 15-20 minutes on the computer. After the material planned for 15 minutes, an intermediate stage of 15-20 minutes will

be held. During this period, taking into account the fatigue of the children, classes are held without computers. In these classes conducted without a computer, riddles, various interesting games, practical activities (for example, cutting letters with scissors, teaching to write on paper) are held.

The use of multimedia computer technology in the educational process helps children to acquire and strengthen their knowledge of the subject, and to develop their computer literacy.

The use of multimedia technologies in the educational process in pre-school educational organizations has the feature of attracting children's attention more. Multimedia education has been proven to be effective in simultaneously seeing and hearing, as well as learning by doing. In the process of using a computer, children's logical thinking develops, their enthusiasm for learning increases, and their outlook is formed. One of the pedagogical aspects of computer didactic games is their educational nature. During the game, the student participates simultaneously in the game and receives a certain level of education. In some games, knowledge is demonstrated through exercises. For example: In the game of stacking shapes, firstly, according to the task of the game, the child finds what shape is formed as a result of stacking the shapes, and secondly, according to the teacher's task, the number of shapes performs the tasks of counting, telling what shapes look like and their names, distinguishing colors (educational aspect). In addition, by using a "mouse", the student develops the skills of working on a computer and increases computer literacy, ability to solve problems, use of innovative technology methods, directs to finding the right solution to problems.

The main form of training is the use of multimedia technology in literacy training of pre-school groups. The use of multimedia technology in teaching literacy to children of pre-school preparation groups is mainly carried out in three ways.

1. With the help of computer and its programs, didactic tools are prepared, then Internet and distance education materials are used.

2. Children are taught new material based on the direct dialogue method with the participation of a computer. It should be noted that a 6-7-year-old child is not able to work on a computer like an adult. Therefore, it is appropriate to use the dialogue method in learning new material in preschool educational organizations.

3. Indirect dialogue - multimedia technology is implemented on the basis of dialogue with a computer in a virtual information environment. In this, the material is studied independently by the children, the material is

repeated independently, exercises are performed independently, multimedia computer games are performed independently, and the child performs the exercises, repeating tasks and games set by the computer can achieve its goal.

Multimedia education is an effective way to help children learn foreign languages easily. Children can learn foreign languages by seeing, hearing, and doing. It is necessary to develop didactic support for teaching foreign languages to children of preschool age using multimedia and game technologies.

Multimedia education can be organized not only in the preschool education organization, but also in the family circle in cooperation with parents. For this, the educator should give advice to parents on how to use this education, based on his pedagogical skills. For example, nowadays there are many types of games based on multimedia, through which children can distinguish colors, count, and form ideas about the whole world. Education based on multimedia should be appropriate for the child's age. Parents should pay attention to what kind of games their children are playing and support their child's interest in mobile games and ensure that they use games that increase their knowledge. But it is appropriate to follow the time when using multimedia games, as it is the norm of every process, because it can have an adverse effect on children's health. It is necessary to follow the rules of use and familiarize the parents with these rules. Only then the result will be appropriate for the goal.

To sum up, today the main task of educators of preschool education organizations is to further develop children's abilities, increase their logical thinking and prepare them for school education. Therefore, in the technology-based era, children cannot be limited to traditional methods of education. It should be said that the use of multimedia in the educational process has many advantages in increasing the effectiveness of education compared to traditional education. It is one of the most important requirements of the present time that an educator and parent should be able to properly use the conditions and opportunities created today, to be able to properly use these technologies in teaching children. To fulfill these requirements, pedagogues should be able to work on themselves for the future generation and adapt new methods of teaching to the interests of children.

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